

A protocol for conducting a survey on existing approaches tackling uncertainty in self-adaptive systems in practice

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1 Research objectives

Software systems are subject to continuous changes due to changing requirements and the dynamics of the system context. Engineering such complex software systems is often difficult as the available knowledge at design time is not adequate to anticipate all the runtime conditions. As a consequence, the software system will encounter a certain level of uncertainty after deployment. In the context of this work, we define uncertainty as those instances in which the system's behavior deviates from how it is expected to function in normal circumstances. This uncertainty may originate from a variety of sources such as ambiguity regarding the availability of resources (e.g., number of available servers), operating conditions that the system will face at runtime (e.g., noisy networks), and the emergence of new requirements while the system is operating (e.g., higher availability).

One way to deal with uncertainty is to design systems that can adapt themselves at runtime, when the required knowledge is accessible: self-adaptive systems (SASs). Self-adaptive systems are capable of autonomously modifying their runtime behavior to deal with dynamic system context, and changing or new system requirements in order to provide dependable, and recoverable systems [1]. Self-adaptive systems achieve this capability by means of an adaptation software that uses reflective models of the system, its environment, and its goals; the adaptation software monitors the running system to detect problems, identify solutions, and apply adaptation actions to modify the system.

1.1 Problem statement and justification

To design and conduct this survey we followed the guidelines presented in [4]. The objective of this survey is to explore the current state of approaches used to handle uncertainty in practice in the domain of self-adaptive systems. The survey will be cross-sectional.

The result of this study is complementary to our previous work on the subject of uncertainty []. In [] we conducted a systematic literature review to survey the current state of research regarding uncertainty in self-adaptive systems, and presented a classification framework for the concept of uncertainty and its different types and categories, and sources of uncertainty in this domain. The results suggested that although researchers consider changes of system goals as one of the main sources of uncertainty in self-adaptive systems, studies rarely explore details of these changes explicitly and often overlook how changes in system goals may affect quality concerns trade-offs. Our results also indicate that uncertainty in this particular domain is often explored at scenario level regardless of whether it emerges during design-time or runtime.

To formally specify the purpose of this work, we use Goal-Question-Metric (GQM) paradigm [] to define the goal of our survey:

Analyze approaches used for handling uncertainty **for the purpose of** characterization **with respect to** the notion and sources of uncertainty, the characteristics of the approaches and how

they handle quality attributes **from the point of view of experts**¹ in **the context of** self-adaptive systems.

The result of this survey will help us to identify the gap between self-adaptive systems in practice and theory, potential inconsistencies and contradictions of existing methods in literature and methods applied in practice, and pinpoint areas for improvement.

1.2 Main research questions

We pose the following high level research questions to investigate the current state of experts' understanding of uncertainty as well as the approaches used to handle uncertainty in self-adaptive systems.

Table 1- Main research questions of the survey.

Research Question	Purpose
RQ1: What is the perception of experts on uncertainty in self-adaptive systems?	We pose this research question to better understand how experts define uncertainty and its sources in self-adaptive systems.
RQ2: What approaches do experts use to mitigate uncertainty and tackle specific sources of uncertainty in practice?	We pose this research question to get an overview of existing approaches dealing with uncertainty. With this question we aim at: 1) identifying the most common approaches used to resolve uncertainty, 2) identifying the sources of uncertainty for which the approaches are used, 3) investigating whether the approach is used during design-time and/or run-time, and 4) whether or not uncertainty is handled in a systematic or ad-hoc manner.
RQ3: How do existing approaches handle non-functional requirements ² and their trade-offs?	We pose this question to investigate how current approaches tackling uncertainty treat quality concerns of the system: 1) whether or not non-functional requirements and their trade-offs are taken into account, and 2) if/how quality assurance is supported after adaptation.

¹ In the rest of this document we use the term “expert” to refer to experts in domain of self-adaptive systems who are experienced in design, development and implementation of self-adaptation methods.

² Note that in this work we use quality concerns, and non-functional requirements interchangeably.

2 Designing and Conducting the Survey

Figure x gives an overview of the main activities we take on in order to design and conduct the survey. At the highest level, there are four main activities: creating and testing the questionnaire, finding the sample, contacting the participants, and analysis and report of the survey. In the following section we explain these activities in detail.

Figure 1 - Designing and conducting the survey, a high level overview.

3 Developing a Survey Instrument

In this section we present our survey instrument. To conduct the survey we will use a questionnaire to extract information from our target audience.

3.1 Designing questionnaire

In the following we first explain the process we followed to create our questionnaire and then put forward the finalized version of the questionnaire.

3.1.1 Questionnaire

In table 2 we present questions to be sent to the sample of our survey.

Table 2 - Questionnaire to be send to the sample.

RQ	ID	Sub Question	Type of answer	Priority
What is uncertainty				
RQ1	SQ1.0	Do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "If uncertainty did not exist, there would be no need for self-adaptive systems."	Agree/disagree - Free text	Medium
RQ1	SQ1.1	How do you define uncertainty in the context of self-adaptive systems? What are the two most common sources of uncertainty that you encountered when developing/evaluating self-adaptive systems	Free text	High
RQ1	SQ1.2	Do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "Self-adaptive systems tend to face certain sources of uncertainty more often than others". If your response is agree, which types of sources? Please explain your answer.	Agree/disagree - Free text	Medium
Mitigating uncertainty				
RQ2	SQ2.1	While dealing with uncertainty, do you think it should be tackled at design-time or run-time?	Design time / runtime / both Free text	High
RQ2	SQ2.2	When engineering self-adaptive systems, do you apply particular approaches to mitigate uncertainty? If your answer is yes, please explain what are the sources of uncertainty and the mitigation approach(es) applied.	Free text	High
RQ2	SQ2.3	Continue on your answer to the previous question, are these sources of uncertainty addressed in a systematic way (i.e., using a structured well-defined approach) or ad-hoc (i.e., on a case by case basis)? If your answer is 'systematic', give one or two examples. If your answer is 'ad-hoc' can you explain briefly whether and how this needs to be improved?	Standardized / ad-hoc /depends on the type of the source of uncertainty Free text	Medium

RQ2	SQ2.4	Consider a scenario in which a self-adaptive system needs to deal with several sources of uncertainty. When dealing with such multiple sources of uncertainty would you prioritise them? If your answer is yes, please select an option ³ or explain your answer.	a: The first identified SoU is handled first. b: SoU with a higher impact on utility gets a higher priority. c: SoU with a higher impact on specific NFRs gets a higher priority. d: SoU with a higher impact on specific system functionality gets a higher priority e. other (free text)	Medium
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Trade-offs and impact

RQ3	SQ3.1	While tackling uncertainty in your work, do you explicitly investigate how non-functional requirements of the system will be affected? If your answer is no, please motivate why not. If your answer is yes, please explain how you achieve this.	Yes/No Free text	High
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RQ3	SQ3.2	When dealing with uncertainty in the self-adaptive systems you have been developing, do you use any method to provide evidence that the system satisfies its stated functional and non-functional requirements under uncertainty? If your answer is yes, please explain what methods you use.	1) Human-driven approaches : Formal, proof, Simulation 2) System-driven approaches: Runtime verification, Sanity checks, Contracts 3) Hybrid approaches: Model checking, Testing 4) Other (Free text)	High
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³ Respondents could select from the following options: a.The first identified source of uncertainty is handled first (i.e., first come first serve), b.The source of uncertainty with a higher impact on the overall utility of the system gets a higher priority, c. The uncertainty with a higher impact on specific non-functional requirements gets a higher priority, d. The uncertainty with a higher impact on specific system functionality gets a higher priority, e. other (free text).

3.1.2 Execution method

We first retrieve email addresses of all the experts included in our sample as described in section 2.1. Next, we contact them by sending an invitation to make a request to participate in our survey.

4 Survey Instrument Evaluation

The protocol of this survey (i.e., this document) is reviewed and refined iteratively by three authors, and then will be externally reviewed by a few other researchers for validity check.

It is important to evaluate our survey before reaching out to the target audience for data collection. Therefore, we check the validity of the questionnaire to examine its understandability and content. There are two major aspects to this evaluation:

1. Validity and completeness of the questionnaire.
2. Clarity of the posed questions.

The first aspect refers to technical validity and usefulness of the questions. In order to examine the validity of the questions (i.e., technical validity), and inspect whether or not the questionnaire will result in the collection of required data (i.e., usefulness) to fulfill the goal of the survey (i.e., answering the main research questions), we will perform a pilot test to evaluate the questions. To conduct the test, we will ask experts in domain of self-adaptive systems and software architecture to review our questionnaire and provide us with feedback.

The second aspect helps to investigate whether or not the questions are comprehensible. To that end, we will perform pilot tests by inviting our research group members to take part in the pilot to identify potential points of ambiguity in our questionnaire.

5 Documentation

To document our survey, we follow the strategy presented in []. [] suggest to follow two main stages:

1. Writing an initial descriptive document called questionnaire specification.
2. Updating the protocol to reflect how the survey was conducted.

The first stage refers to creation of this document (i.e., survey protocol) in which we specify the objective of the study, research questions and the rationale for posing the questions, and the description of the evaluation process (i.e., sections 2,3, and 4).

The second stage refers to the activities to be performed after the questionnaire is administered. In this stage the protocol should be updated to specify how the survey was administered, who were the participants of the survey, the completeness of questionnaires' process, and how the follow up procedure is conducted.

6 Obtaining Valid Data

To check the validity of collected responses we use two different filtering means. First, we use the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in table x to filter the responses.

Table 3 - Data validity inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria

I1: the respondent is experienced in design, development and/or deployment of self-adaptive systems.

Exclusion criteria

E1: Inconsistency in responses.

E2: Incomprehensible response.

After filtering the collected responses based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria, we assess whether or not enough responses are retrieved to conduct meaningful analysis.

7 Sample and Population

To create our sample, we use non-probabilistic methods. Non-probabilistic samples are created when participants are believed to be representative of the population and the target population is very specific and of limited availability. We specifically select the Convenience sampling method (i.e., a type of non-probabilistic sampling method which aims at reaching out to a group of people whom are relatively easy to contact) in order to obtain respondents who are available and willing to participate our survey.

Specifically, we will contact experts who are experienced in design, development, and implementation of SASs. We use both a targeted approach (researchers with prominent work in SASs) and a general approach (the SEAMS mailing list). SEAMS is the most prominent venue regarding SASs, as the SEAMS community consists of the leading experts in design of SASs.

8 Sampling Method

To create our sample, we choose to use non-probabilistic methods. Non-probability samples are created when participants are believed to be representative of the population and the target population is very specific and of limited availability []. We specifically select the *Convenience sampling* method in order to obtain respondents who are available and willing to participate our survey.

8.1 Response Rate

After filtering the responses, we assess the remaining data to ensure that enough responses are retrieved and recorded to obtain meaningful results from the survey. Following the definition provided in [], response rate is the proportion of the participants who responded to the number of people who were approached. The resulting response rate should be roughly 60%. In case of a low response rate, we follow the strategies suggested in [] to improve response rates.

9 Analyzing Survey Data

The extracted data should be read and categorized in a tabulated format to be analyzed. We plan to perform descriptive statistics to synthesize our data. Descriptive analysis is used to present quantitative descriptions for the extracted data, and to summarize the data in a comprehensible and manageable format to answer the research questions.

We will use descriptive statistics (e.g., mean, standard deviation, correlation, etc.), where applicable, to represent results in simpler format and combined with plot representations of the analyzed data we use them to answer the research questions.

Including open-ended questions in our questionnaire provides the participants with the opportunity to freely articulate their perceptions and experiences regarding uncertainty in self-adaptive systems. Free text answers (i.e., qualitative data) collected using the questionnaire will be recoded in excel files to be analyzed later. We use constant comparative method to analyze the answers to open-ended questions. This method offers the means to analyze the textual responses which are not collected based on pre-defined categories. To analyze the collected data through open questions, the categories and the relationship between the categories are derived from the collected textual responses by inductive reasoning[]. This will allow us to investigate the possibility of integrating the participants' responses into a model explaining how currently uncertainty is being handled in self-adaptive systems in practice. More precisely, we will use coding to capture data's essence and arranging them in a systematic order for further synthesis. This codification allows us to identify potential patterns and categorize the collected qualitative data and segregate them in order to consolidate meaning and explanation.

10 References

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[5] <https://qdatraining.com/defining-the-constant-comparison-method/>